

Adoption of Team Coaching Competencies for Innovative Translation and Foreign Language Instruction: Polylingual and Polycultural Dimensions in Higher Education

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ABSTRACT: The contemporary world is subject to waves of highly rated turbulences and demand volatility in the market of educational services. In the recent decades, Ukraine as a developing state has witnessed varied response from educators, students, observers, bloggers as to the content and quality of education. The paper aims to elaborate the surface scratching recommendations for the development of an educational policy, which may be eligible for adoption at universities, endorsing modernisation of content and structure of higher education inside and outside Ukraine by means of developing, growing and applying coaching mind-set for teaching and learning processes. First, this refers to growing efficiency in communication models by foreign language (FL) teachers (irrespective of the field) and foreign language instructors (teaching foreign languages, languages for specific purposes in foreign languages, and translation) in giving lectures and moderating polycultural and polylingual classes. Second, it links to fostering culturological, axiological, intercommunicative values for polycultural communication in various languages, if applicable, between the teacher and the student and vice versa, the teacher and the teacher, the student and the student, etc. Team coaching may be treated one of the fastest growing disciplines in the coaching profession; and for the higher education, it is becoming increasingly important Team coaching competencies as hard skill of a modern FL / LSP teacher may enable a U-turn in the educational market as viewed in the light of demotivated students, losing interest in an academic degree, or gaining qualifications within the university walls. Team coaching defined as partnering in a co-creative and reflective process with a team (class) on its dynamics and relationships in a way that inspires them to maximize their abilities and potential in order to reach their common purpose and shared goals, may well fit into class instruction of the modern era.

KEYWORDS: Team Coaching Competencies, Foreign Language Instruction, Foreign Language (FL), Translation, Polycultural and Polylingual Classes, Quality Education.

INTRODUCTION

The contemporary world is subject to waves of highly rated turbulences and demand volatility in the market of educational services [8; 24]. In the recent decades, Ukraine as a developing state has witnessed varied response from educators, students, observers, bloggers as to the content and quality of education [25, p.434 – 459; 17; 22]. More challenges are yet to come. Covid-19 with the pandemic regulations locally and internationally, online courses and remote study made education stakeholders take it seriously and address the issue immediately. High schools, colleges, universities, research centres have to adopt to the “new normal” as current day restrictions in connection to the pandemic situation would hardly encourage anyone to study harder; the generation shifts from ‘baby-boomers’ to ‘X’, ‘Y’ and ‘Z’ have brought their impact on economy, cultural and life values, thus, leading to change in cognitive and behavioural patterns [19; 30; 32; 33]. Lastly, digitization and communications era may not be ignored at all, which leaves much ambiguity as to analytical treatment of digital skills being seen of advantage or disadvantage in the day [1].

There are ways and techniques that can be used to advance higher education with enhanced quality and enriched content [16]. At the same time, these ways and methods may apply as part of learning curricula given the fact that soft skills in the twenty-first century give no way to hard skills.

Intercultural communication in language teaching has always been part of the content plane. One may not train to become a foreign language teacher or foreign language instructor (FL teacher), teacher / instructor of languages for specific purposes (LSP teacher / instructor), a teacher in translation courses or a translator unless they meet some criteria and follow the rules [24]. Students first are acquainted with not only language levels, but also learn customs and traditions, culture, folklore, literature, lifestyles of the people which language is of interest and for mastery [27; 28].

Global mobility dearly contributes to the discussed. Cross-border travelling and employment, education in a home country or abroad no longer arise impossible. On the contrary, with varying lower to higher quality education, students and parents may

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decide which university may satisfy the needs and a wide range of schools start competing for every student ready to consider relevant programs and join the course / enter the university [22]. Therefore, polylingualism and polyculturalism are commonplace today.

Classrooms transform, i.e. they become diversified in both the aspects – language and culture. It means that the curricula should be subject to changes as well. The questions arise; solutions are not always at hand.

As a prerequisite of contemporary communication and updating methodological technologies in the field of education, the paper considers adoption of coaching methodological portfolio a solution to many challenges faced today by the educational market.

That is part of methodology, which would move the needle and appear a game-changer for countering unexpected changes and meeting the educational demand after the Covid-19 and remote study repercussions. Speaking of international classrooms under students' mobility programs, which at the same time are polylingual and poly- / multicultural classrooms, FL teachers and instructors, teachers and translation and languages for specific purposes have to also adapt to the changes, and most probably see to having some courses and trainings, which may help them bring more value to the class [28; 31]. Knowledge and theory by a class teacher play no crucial role inasmuch the internet and open source media provide their audience with much data upon request. Hence, non-understanding of higher education value when seeking a degree and winning qualifications, as major skills students / adults may acquire independently [3; 5; 6].

That said it is believed there is only a single but challenging way to attract highly motivated students and provide them with the necessary educational service, i.e. properly arranged and structured curricula and exciting content [12; 13]. In short, teachers make into partners rather than remain superior as distinguished with their professionalism, field competence, knowledge and skills [18; 20]. The goal of higher education would chain-transform (SS means students):

Fig. 1. Changing teaching need in methodology: chronological facet (Author's model)

For the purpose specified above, team coaching may be treated one of the fastest growing disciplines in the coaching profession [14]; and for the higher education, it is becoming increasingly important.

The aim of this article is to elaborate the surface scratching recommendations for the development of an educational policy, which may be eligible for adoption at universities, endorsing modernisation of content and structure of higher education inside and outside Ukraine by means of developing, growing and applying coaching mind-set for teaching and learning processes.

First, this refers to growing efficiency in communication models by foreign language teachers (irrespective of the field) and foreign language instructors (teaching foreign languages, languages for specific purposes in foreign languages, and translation) in giving lectures and moderating polycultural and polylingual classes.

Second, it links to fostering culturological, axiological, intercommunicative values for polycultural communication in various languages, if applicable, between the teacher and the student and vice versa, the teacher and the teacher, the student and the student, etc.

That will definitely lead to enhanced quality education, which is inclusive of fundamental values based on ethics in polycultural and polylingual communication, motivate students for e-learning and encourage faculty (teachers, instructors, trainers, etc.) for application of cutting-edge technologies in their educational interactions. Education management in the digital environment of a modern university would be destined to exercise success.

METHODOLOGY AND LITERATURE REVIEW

Methodology and material of the study

To start with, it is necessary to address the definition of team coaching as widely accepted and referred to in professional communities. ICF Global, or International Coaching Federation, introduced additional model of coaching competencies for those

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coaches who work with teams. That means that the generally known definition of coaching is broadened, as the coachee (one who seeks and receives coaching effect) is no longer an individual as one person; it is now a group of people that pursue the common goal. Thus, ICF Global defines team coaching as “partnering in a co-creative and reflective process with a team on its dynamics and relationships in a way that inspires them to maximize their abilities and potential in order to reach their common purpose and shared goals” [14].

This research and research findings absolutely build on and adopt the above definition of team coaching, with an only indication that it is necessary to differentiate for the limited scope of discussion in a paper between the group coaching and team coaching, where both stand for:

- (i) A group of students in a polylingual and/or polycultural classroom,
- (ii) Faculty members including FL and LSP teachers (instructors), translation teachers and experts, and so on.

The research methods and techniques applied take to the classical research methods [3; 28]. The analysis of scientific literature helped follow and either agree or disagree on concepts of polyculturalism as presented in academia. Synthesis and analysis were used in general theoretical and applied aspects; the descriptive method as applied helped describe the suggested approach to modernisation of content and structure of the higher education under the existing decaying framework in connection with the research topic. Moreover, the research methodology makes an integrated approach where the use of analytical, descriptive, structural synthetic methods apply.

The main material used and to be underlying the conceptual framework in the study is ICF Global’s model of Team Coaching Competencies, and as to be exemplified in the findings, Competency 1 – Coach “Demonstrates Ethical Practice”, in particular [14]. The model discusses supplements to criteria and markers of professional coachwork and explains the background. In the study case, it is considered a FL teacher / instructor, an LSP teacher / instructor, a translator / translation teacher would adopt competencies of a professional coach / mentor / supervisor, etc.

Literature review

Following the Executive Summary on *Defining Quality in Education* (2000), it is critical to focus on the systemic approach to the concept and definition of quality education [2]. It means that education should be treated as a complex system, which makes integral part of the global society and serves the community needs. Quality education integrates all possible contexts, fundamental of which are political, economic and cultural. From this viewpoint, each state in the world is responsible for legal and financial regulation in the educational market, hence the political and economic dimensions [2; 6; 8]. However, in order to implement any key role of the state, cultural background would play its role, as well. Accounting for processes of global mobility, non-discrimination and striving for global assimilation to collaborate on sustainable growth in the future, polycultural and polylingual dimensions come to the frontline; role of a classroom teacher as a leader becomes an everyday necessity [21; 29; 17].

Overall, all the above-mentioned contexts and dimensions are interdependent and contribute to the society, influencing each other, influencing change, influencing driving trends for the future developments in the world.

Quality education in the executive report (UNICEF) includes five major criteria [2], which underlie the determination for modernizing structure and content of the contemporary methodology in the educational market.

- 1) “Learners who are healthy, well-nourished and ready to participate and learn, and supported in learning by their families and communities” [2, p. 4];

Health and well-being of students are critical. It is apparent that only then students can participate in the learning process eagerly and feel support from family, fellows and faculty members.

The educational environment in Ukraine suffered immensely with the unprecedented developments in March 2019. The issues addressed locally and globally help gain some equilibrium; however, much more was left to be desired. Health was number one on priority list:

“Between the 3rd of January 2020 and the 26th of July 2021, 2,248,663 of COVID-19 cases were confirmed in Ukraine, including 52,849 deaths, according to the World Health Organisation. Excess mortality data in Ukraine, however, suggest a figure somewhat above 80,000 deaths caused by the pandemic. [...] As of the 22nd of July, Ukraine had detected 6Delta cases. The government officially announced that health authorities have reagents for detecting the Delta variant, which is suspected to be circulating in the country since June 2021” [30].

It is clear from the above that the state makes all possible and reasonable efforts to cope with the existing situation: “The national vaccination campaign began on 24 February 2021. However, although the pace of vaccination has started to pick-up since the beginning of June, Ukraine remains the country with the lowest vaccination coverage in Europe. As of the 21st of July, 4.4 million doses were administered, and 1.56 million people, or 3.6% of the total population, were fully vaccinated” [30].

As discussed, criterion 1 in connection to quality education in Ukraine is set and propagated; however, the consequences of the Covid-19 pandemic keep influencing not only physiological health of students and faculty members, but also emotional and psychological. It becomes challenging to find best ways and solutions to ensure “learners are supported in learning by their

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families and communities” [2]. That definitely leads to demotivation and discourages students and teachers in general to engage proactively in the learning and teaching processes, correspondingly [22; 16; 10; 11; 32].

- 2) Another criterion as set out in the Executive Summary for UNICEF runs as follows: “Environments that are healthy, safe, protective and gender-sensitive, and provide adequate resources and facilities” [2, p. 4] can speak out of quality education.

To respond and meet standards of quality education, it is seen apparent that leadership is a key [29; 20; 17]. In the times of pandemic and remote study, changing educational systems strongly require leadership approach [12; 10; 21]. Leadership coaching can shadow crisis management and even substitute it as a blended model in some time.

Thus, Coldwell (2017) sees ethical leadership as a necessary ingredient for successful crisis management. His work ‘Ethical Leadership in Crisis Management: The Role of University Education’ outlines remedial steps that can be taken by university and high school administration when faced by crises [4].

It is agreed with Coldwell that such remedial steps are simply the “bricks and mortar” of effective crisis management [4] but in order to mitigate risks and manage crises successfully, there’s a burning need in properly manifested leadership, which the author calls the “pulsating soul” of effective crisis management. Moreover, leadership built on ethical values and beliefs – “ethical leadership” can become this “necessary moral compass for the initiation and sustained directional focus” [4]. Shynkaruk, Chakovskyy and Meteshkin move it further and underline the critical value of system approach to researching integration processes in higher education of Ukraine [28]; Laloux (2014) focusses on the model of reinventing organizations and highlights the value of creating organizations that will be inspired by the next stage in human consciousness [17]. To that extent, any metamorphoses that take place in the human mind expressly link to coaching methodology, and when adopted and exercised properly, would lead to development, growth and success [9; 18].

At large, looking at inevitable response to global developments and in education, in particular, Coldwell suggests the ethical leadership model as first discusses a model of crisis management by providing examples from a number of best practice case studies and briefs ways and possibilities of reducing financial losses to the organizations if correctly implemented by ethical leaders. Next, the study displays how ethical leadership may make part of the university curricula for postgraduate students, the ways it can be “nurtured through specific ethics-oriented postgraduate university instruction” [4]. It is reasonable enough to adopt first ethical leadership as part of cognitive and behavioral patterns for the trained staff at universities, and then start including material and practical tips into the university curricula.

- 3) Digital competency is a ‘must’ these days, which points out to a need of polycultural classrooms to adopt fast and efficient tools for in-class, out-of-class and cross-border communication, updated learning and teaching methodology [1; 25]. This statement duly aligns with the third criterion of quality education by UNICEF:

“Content that is reflected in relevant curricula and materials for the acquisition of basic skills, especially in the areas of literacy, numeracy and skills for life, and knowledge in such areas as gender, health, nutrition, HIV/AIDS prevention and peace” [2, p. 4].

Content of the relevant curricula should be diversified, rich and innovative. From a structural perspective and understanding needs of the modern digital society, it becomes evident that digital skills in the form of ICT implementation at universities and re-designing models for e-learning have made into skills for life, which equal to literacy and numeracy [1; 25]. That said, the quality content includes a set of internal and external factors, which aim to enhance high standards of future education.

Noskova et al. (2016) describe the specifics of the IRNet project, under which the authors analyse and compare the approaches and procedures of education quality evaluation at the universities. The project methodology included survey analysis made from responses by teachers from three universities in Poland, Russia, and Ukraine [25]. The other reports [6; 8; 10; 11; 25] emphasize the burning need in quality change for the educational market lest it should collapse.

- 4) The other criterion based on “Processes through which trained teachers use child-centred teaching approaches in well-managed classrooms and schools and skilful assessment to facilitate learning and reduce disparities” [2, p. 4] is crucial these days.

The student-oriented approach will enable FL teachers, LSP teachers / instructors, translation teachers and so on to adjust the existing curricula and teaching methods, design new ones to meet the criteria of quality education, and align them with the individual and group (class) goals in a polycultural and polylingual classroom.

Teacher’s role may not be exaggerated today. Makino (2018) reasonably mentions that “teachers are one of the demotivating factors for students who learn English” [22].

The literature studied shows that there are too many factors in the polylingual and /or polycultural classroom, which may easily influence students and demotivate them [16; 22; 32]. Majority of such factors link to teachers’ performance in class. It is relevant to note that such studies lack information on remedial education. Oftentimes, research findings identify and analyse the survey data, focus on advantages and disadvantages of education and unveil the problem of students’ demotivation. Even fewer

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works touch upon teachers' demotivation and/or encouraging drivers to perform better and proactively in the polylingual and polycultural classrooms. It is regular that the results round up to a list of some characteristics or description of situations, which demotivate and discourage students to learn eagerly. Similarly, Makino's research findings specify demotivating role or behavior of teachers. The list includes examples when teachers are not sufficiently enthusiastic about helping students understand and make students think that they cannot keep up with the class. Some more describe classes when teachers do not show interest in students, and teach English in a boring manner. Another demotivating factor lies with teachers who do not consider the anxiety of students with low English proficiency in polylingual and polycultural classrooms [22].

It is fair to state that these factors do demotivate students and hardly make teachers engage more. Makino's suggestion for changing a situation is to make teachers reflect more on themselves, along with reflexion on their teaching methods. This will lead, according to the scholar, to improved attitude of class towards the teacher and teaching after reflective analysis will raise students' motivation [22].

Such proposal and recommendations look sound, and it is necessary to note that reflective practices are core in the coaching competencies portfolio.

5) The last but not least criterion for quality education is as follows: "Outcomes that encompass knowledge, skills and attitudes, and are linked to national goals for education and positive participation in society" [2, p. 4].

Personal goals, university goals in higher educational sector and national goals if aligned will lead the change.

The state strategy plays an incredibly high role in science and education. At the current stage of its development, the Ukrainian education system neither "meets the individual/social needs nor it is prepared to face the economic challenges or world trends" [8]. The Ukrainian government endeavours to carry out relevant steps and actions associated with the systemic transformation. These steps aim to ensure a new quality of education at each level: from preschool to higher and adult (lifelong learning) education.

Moreover, as stated in the Education and Science Reform on government portal, "the science sector reform is designed to stop research isolation and stagnation, create a demand for quality researcher training and inventions in basic and applied sciences, reduce the gap between research and practice, integrate Ukrainian higher education and science in the European Research Area" [8].

A lot is being done. For example, the reform prioritises the following areas in the Ukrainian educational market: (i) affordable and quality pre-school education; (ii) New Ukrainian School; (iii) modern professional education; (iv) quality higher education and development of adult education; (v) development of science and innovation [8].

The described explains what is being transformed in Ukraine in the educational sector; the above stated clarifies why these changes are necessary and sets perspectives for meeting the highest standards of quality education in future. However, the reports and relevant sections are silent as to the ways of meeting the highly-set objectives.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Since the "what" content that requires change has been discussed, as well as it was highlighted why the Ukrainian educational system is in sharp need of reforms, the gap remains with "how" it is possible to bring this change, implement it and make it work in future.

Following the aim of the study and within the scope of the objectives set for the paper, it is important to refresh that a solution is seen with the communication model between all stakeholders of the educational process. Reading Collins' *Good to Great: Why Some Companies Make the Leap... and Others Don't*, it is agreed with Einzig that the future is with coaching, and coaching is the future [9]. Education management makes no exception; on the contrary, with the help of feasible transformations in education, coaching will bring faster and more efficient results to all other organizations and businesses, thus, advancing economy and strengthening the political dialogue in the world.

Therefore, the research findings rely on the suggested model of teacher's thinking and behaviour in a polylingual and polycultural class. It is not argued that the old patterned teaching methodology becomes inappropriate and disappear. This model aims to introduce some recommendations to an FL teacher / instructor, LSP teacher / instructor, translation expert / teacher in a polylingual and polycultural classroom as to modifying the teaching process. It can be possible via amending the teaching / training / instruction process with a student-oriented approach and progressive coaching technologies.

At first, the teacher's main role under the proposed model is no longer with teaching the class; nor even is it with teaching students to learn independently (see Fig. 1 above). As a leader, an FL teacher / instructor, LSP teacher / instructor, translation expert / teacher in a polylingual and polycultural classroom partners with students and helps them get acquainted with themselves through reflective methods. Students find out their individual best, fastest and most efficient ways to learn under such coaching supervision of their class teacher. That the new and modern version of such an FL teacher / instructor, LSP teacher / instructor, translation expert / teacher in a polylingual and polycultural classroom works with class as a whole is crucially important.

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Nevertheless, the model presupposes that in a coaching style communication the teacher / mentor / supervisor, as relevant per context, helps each student identify and set their personal goals in the subject for a semester or academic year. At the same time, the students altogether, accounting for personal goals in education, set the common group goal. The FL / LSP teacher and /or translation teacher explains to class that the class success depends on achievement of individual goals. The faster and more efficient their performance is, the sooner students may achieve the group goal. As clarified, this model eliminates demotivation and educational procrastination as teaching and learning threats and creates good foundations for building teams and demonstrating advantages of teamwork to the students.

Leadership is important [29; 20], ethical leadership in education is crucial [4]. Ethical leadership in the teacher's portfolio of updated competencies for foreign language instruction and students' acquisition of knowledge and practical skills becomes the hard core.

The below are the recommendations driven from the study results and based on Competency 1 of Team Coaching [14].

In a polycultural and polylingual classroom, in order to grow students' motivation and unveil full capacity of talent, it is prerequisite that a modern FL teacher / instructor, LSP teacher / instructor, a teacher, who delivers lectures and workshop on translation studies, adopts the following for fast track progress and efficient performance of the polycultural / polylingual students. Thus, Fig. 2 outlines the FL / LSP teacher's foundational competency in leading a polycultural and/or polylingual class:

- 1) (s)he treats and communicates with the polycultural / polylingual class as a single entity,
- 2) (s)he stops teaching and starts leading a class, communicating equally with everyone in a coaching way,
- 3) (s)he shares knowledge and skills for information, asks for feedback and in a reflective way stimulates class development,
- 4) (s)he moderates and instructs where needed, leaving the other educational space for individual and group freedom to choose the best appropriate methods for communication, learning, exercising, training, and providing feedback,
- 5) (s)he fosters trust and transparency, by choosing a partnering role rather than teaching.

Fig. 2. Criteria of the FL / LSP teacher's foundational competency:Fast and efficient translation and foreign language instruction

According to the team coaching competencies model, Competency 1: Demonstrates Ethical Practice, - defines the concept as the coach, who meets this competency, understands and consistently applies coaching ethics and standards of coaching.

For the research aim and objectives, in a polycultural and/or polylingual classroom a modern FL teacher / instructor, LSP teacher / instructor, a teacher, who delivers lectures and workshop on translation studies, understands and consistently applies coaching ethics. Under this coaching ethics s/he cannot impose his/her teaching methods on students irrespective of his/her level of professionalism and expertise, years of teaching experience and academic work. Moreover, a modern FL teacher / instructor, LSP teacher / instructor, a teacher, who delivers lectures and workshop on translation studies, undertakes to meet and keep standards of newly designed model of instruction and training with all due respect to each student and a group.

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The designated model envisages the criteria, by meeting which in relation to the FL / LSP / translation teacher, it may be possible to state that the quality shift in methodology for acquisition and instruction of foreign languages and translation in a polycultural and/or polylingual classroom has taken place.

The list is as below:

- 1) The FL / LSP / translation teacher in a polycultural and/or polylingual classroom communicates with the class as a single entity, demonstrating integrity and respect to each student at the same time.

Having learnt from a coaching style communication with each particular student his / her personal goals, a modern and creative FL / LSP / translation teacher asks questions in a thought-provoking way, encouraging class to see something about their personalities, their way of thinking, learning and behaviour, that before was left out and did not come to the forefront of their consciousness.

Having collected the ideas and giving students more time to reflect, a modern and creative FL / LSP / translation teacher partners with students and draws their attention to the fact they are free to ask and answer questions, interrupt and note if something is unclear or gives birth to doubts and fears, etc. All this happens in a co-creative and reflective process.

The goal of such FL / LSP instruction or translation is to work with everyone as part of the team. Such leading and moderating instruction in a polylingual and polycultural class will enable transparency of individual and group goals and result in improved class performance, for each student will be motivated and engaged. Moreover, each student will understand that the group / team success depends on his / her progress, and on the contrary, his / her progress will lead to group / team success.

Still, there are many challenges to creative FL / LSP / translation teacher. First, the modern teacher under the updated instruction model should focus and constantly monitor and observe the group / team dynamics and development of relationships in a polycultural and/or polylingual class, on the one hand. On the other, they should inform the class of what has been noticed as a regular cognitive or behavioural pattern of the class or individual students in a class, and ask the class to consider it and make a decision what to do with that, and elaborate on ways to move forward.

All the communication between the modern FL / LSP / translation teacher and the class happens in a way that inspires students to maximize their abilities and potential in order to reach their common purpose and shared goals. Fig. 3 *Ethical model of instructing a class* illustrates that despite the central position of the teacher's / instructor's role, of pivotal importance is freedom to communicate, share thought and ideas, bring to the top fears and concerns, which is possible with a teacher's competency connected to building feeling trust and safety in a polycultural and/or polylingual environment.

Fig. 3. Ethical model of instructing a class

To briefly conclude on the above, all the students in a polycultural and/or polylingual classroom for a modern FL / LSP / translation teacher is the class (in future, a team), which the teacher / instructor treats as a single entity.

Thus, a polylingual and polycultural class is made up of individual class members, or students, or attendees, and the teacher / instructor ensures each one be heard and play an integral role in class discussions.

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Further, the modern FL / LSP / translation teacher remains objective in all interactions with the class students, class mentors if any, and relevant stakeholders (Head of Department, Head of Faculty, senior staff, etc.). The modern FL / LSP / translation teacher should not be perceived as taking sides with any student, group or subgroup. The modern FL / LSP / translation teacher remains open to what is emerging in the lectures, seminars, webinars, workshops, trainings and so on. The modern FL / LSP / translation teacher is completely honest in all dealings with the class.

Discussions with individual students may occur, even on a regular basis. However, modern FL / LSP / translation teacher ensures that any information shared and disclosed remains confidential to the FL / LSP / translation teacher and the student unless the student allows disclosure of information to others.

- 2) The FL / LSP / translation teacher in a polycultural and/or polylingual classroom maintains the distinction between different development modalities in FL / LSP instruction and translation.

The modern innovative FL / LSP / translation teacher in a polycultural and/or polylingual classroom is well aware of various roles attributable to achieve fast and efficient results with the class. Thus, respective of the lesson's / lecture's / seminar's goal and as agreed with the class, such development scenarios and modalities vary from class teambuilding, class (team) training, class (team) consulting, class (team) mentoring, class (team) supervision, class (team) facilitation, class (team) negotiation for agreement or mediation for conflict resolution, if any, and other classwork development modalities. For illustration, please see Fig. 4 on development modalities in a polycultural and/or polylingual class, expressly relating to roles assigned or assumed by the modern FL / LSP / translation teacher for effective instruction.

Fig. 4. Classwork: development modalities

Classwork development can involve many modalities. For instance, teambuilding can be one of them, which barely happens at the beginning of collaboration between fellows in a polycultural and/or polylingual class, the class and the teacher, etc. Unlike class teambuilding, class consulting may be one form or another of teacher's sharing experience and giving advice and recommendation on some specific topics, e.g. which books to read, which dictionaries to consult, which webinars to attend, etc. Class mentoring looks like group reflexion on mistakes, if any, analysis of the mistakes, ways of avoiding such mistakes in future, as well as observance and comments on success and achievements of the class.

Where necessary, the FL / LSP / translation teacher in a polycultural and/or polylingual classroom partners with other experts when specific knowledge and skill levels are required.

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It is worth noting that such modern FL / LSP / translation teacher in a polycultural and/or polylingual classroom may need to refer students to other professional colleagues and/or invite colleagues and peers as guest lecturers / visiting professors. In addition, under a circumstance they become demotivated, exhausted or feel they are burning out, the modern FL / LSP / translation teacher may also seek and receive assistance from a colleague, who is aware of and uses the coaching instruction model. A professional coach, a mentor and a supervisor can be of help as well, where needed.

- 3) The modern FL / LSP / translation teacher in a polycultural and/or polylingual classroom demonstrates the knowledge and skill needed to practise the specific blend of classwork development modalities.

The modern FL / LSP / translation teacher in a polycultural and/or polylingual classroom acquaints the class with different modalities if necessary and asks students as a team to decide, which form of communication for FL acquisition / instruction / training they believe will suit best under a specific learning context.

It means that a decision is not made by the teacher, although his / her opinion may be similar to that made by the class.

It may be stated that a good FL / LSP / translation teacher in a polycultural and/or polylingual classroom always asks for a choice to be made by students;

An engaging FL / LSP / translation teacher in a polycultural and/or polylingual classroom will ask why the class have decided on that classwork development, in particular; and

The great FL / LSP / translation teacher in a polycultural and/or polylingual classroom will challenge students as to which other contexts and environments they can adopt that choice as a winning and supportive strategy of thinking and behaviour and benefit from it.

Fig. 5 sets out regular professional competencies of the FL / LSP / translation teacher in a polycultural and/or polylingual classroom, which can be accompanied by an upgrade of properly selected ways and tools for efficient communication and performance results under the newly suggested model for FL / LSP instruction and translation.

Fig. 5. Translation / FL / LSP Teacher's Methodological Toolkit of Hard-skill Competencies

The FL / LSP / translation teacher in a polycultural and/or polylingual classroom is sufficiently skilled to competently practise all of the classwork development modalities that the teacher is offering in a lesson / lecture/ workshop as part of a class engagement.

- 4) The modern FL / LSP / translation teacher in a polycultural and/or polylingual classroom is free to adopt more directive classwork development modalities on condition that the other methods are inappropriate or the chosen modalities when exercised fail to bring the expected or designed result.

It means that the FL / LSP / translation teacher in a polycultural and/or polylingual classroom may become more authoritative and instructive only when it is the way to help the class achieve their common goals.

Even with directive ways of leading a class to their goals, it is possible for the FL / LSP / translation teacher in a polycultural and/or polylingual classroom to adopt facilitation in a coaching way.

Fig. 6. Directive class-work development modalities

In general, there are more times when an FL / LSP / translation teacher in a polycultural and/or polylingual classroom will need to be directive than when working with a student on a one-to-one basis or tutoring a student.

It is a good point to remember as keep these instances limited to those opportunities that require a directive approach. It may be especially natural of opportunities to bring students’ awareness to growth areas for the class as a team. Another instance may be to help students understand the team coaching process in educational environment for their learning goals.

It is significant to point out that the class (team) dynamics may vary from class to class. Sometimes it may be positive, other days it may turn negative. It is obvious that many factors may influence class dynamics; and the FL / LSP / translation teacher in a polycultural and/or polylingual classroom then introduces ways to move forward.

These moments for the FL / LSP / translation teacher in a polycultural and/or polylingual classroom of being directive should broaden the students’ perspective as a class (as a team) on their current situation.

- 5) The FL / LSP / translation teacher in a polycultural and/or polylingual classroom maintains trust, transparency, and clarity when fulfilling multiple roles related to class coaching-way instruction of foreign languages and languages for specific purposes, translation included. Everything is carried out as agreed primarily between the teacher and the class.

Fig. 7. Foundational Values for teacher’s role in class

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In the event that an FL / LSP / translation teacher in a polycultural and/or polylingual classroom offers multiple classwork development modalities, the teacher / instructor must be clear about these different roles; and how one role may affect another. Under such scenario, all the class are aware and may act, correspondingly, taking and sharing responsibility with their partner, i.e. the FL / LSP / translation teacher.

CONCLUSIONS

The research findings clearly demonstrate that Team Coaching for polylingual and polycultural classroom empowers students as a single team to work toward continued high performance and ongoing development. Foreign language instruction, instruction of languages for specific purposes and translation may become more progressive and efficient if teaching and learning processes are aligned under the coaching way model of communication.

The adoption of team coaching competencies for foreign language instruction, instruction of languages for specific purposes and translation in a polylingual and polycultural classroom require innovation, flexibility, adaptability and goal alignment between the students and reporting to the instructor in class.

As regards recommendations for the development of an educational policy, which may be eligible for adoption at universities, endorsing modernisation of content and structure of higher education inside and outside Ukraine by means of developing, growing and applying coaching mind-set for teaching and learning processes, in a polycultural and polylingual classroom, in order to grow students' motivation and unveil full capacity of talent, it is prerequisite that a modern FL teacher / instructor, LSP teacher / instructor, a teacher, who delivers lectures and workshop on translation studies, adopts a foundational competency in leading a polycultural and/or polylingual class. That will enable fast track progress and efficient performance of the polycultural / polylingual students.

The findings show that the following modes of communication and behaviour in a polylingual and polycultural classroom will be perspective and lead to fruitful results. The FL teacher / instructor, LSP teacher / instructor, a teacher, who delivers lectures and workshop on translation studies, treats and communicates with the polycultural / polylingual class as a single entity. They stop teaching and start leading a class, communicating equally with everyone in a coaching way. Such teachers share knowledge and skills for information, always ask for feedback and in a reflective way stimulate class development. In addition, they moderate and instruct only where needed, leaving the other educational space for individual and group freedom to choose the best appropriate methods for communication, learning, exercising, training, and providing feedback. Finally, the modern FL teacher / instructor, LSP teacher / instructor, a teacher, who delivers lectures and workshop on translation studies, fosters trust and transparency, by choosing a partnering role rather than teaching.

At the present moment, changing the educational sector in Ukraine occurs with the action plan of tasks, which are being performed under the government strategy. The common goal is to transform Ukrainian education into an innovative environment "where students will learn key skills essential for each modern person to succeed in life, and scientists will have opportunities and resources to conduct research directly contributing to the country's socio-economic and innovative development" [8]. It is believed that with adoption of team coaching competencies as hard skill for future foreign language teacher / instructor, teacher / instructor of languages for specific purposes and a teacher, who delivers lectures and workshop on translation studies, quality of education will increase dramatically.

To understand in which ways to move first among academia for the education reform, and uncover all the potential of the educational sector, more research and in-depth study is required.

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